

STUDIES IN THE CAMPHOR SERIES PART VI.

BY DINESH CHANDRA SEN.

Thiocamphor- α -carboxylic acid, thiocamphor- α -dithiocarboxylic acid and oxy-methylene-thiocamphor have been prepared by the action of carbon dioxide, carbon disulphide and formic ester respectively on sodiothiocamphor. The constitution of these compounds has been established and a few derivatives described.

Sodiothiocamphor has been utilised for the synthesis of isonitrosothiocamphor, bithiocamphor and alkylidene thiocamphors (Sen, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 12, 751; 1936, 13, 523; 1937, 14, 216 etc.). In the present communication the behaviour of carbon dioxide, carbon disulphide and formic ester towards sodiothiocamphor has been described.

When a current of dry carbon dioxide is passed through sodiothiocamphor in benzene-ether medium at 0° , thiocamphor- α -carboxylic acid is obtained as the sodium salt from which the acid can be isolated. *l*-Thiocamphor gives *d*-thiocamphor- α -carboxylic acid, m.p. 125° , $[\alpha]_D^{30}$, 21.03° and *dl*-thiocamphor similarly yields *dl*-carboxylic acid, m.p. 121° . These are fairly stable β -thioketonic acids none of which has hitherto been isolated in the free state. These acids lose carbon dioxide and give the corresponding thiocamphor (*l*- and *dl*- respectively) on distillation in vacuum, a property also shared by their oxygen analogues (cf. Brühl, *Ber.*, 1904, 37, 2074; *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1900, 34, 1; Oddo, *Gazzetta*, 1893, 23, 1, 74; Haller, *Compt. rend.*, 1886, 102, 1477; Bredt and Sand Kuhl, *Annalen*, 1909, 366, 11, etc.).

The colour of the acids (white) as well as their capacity to form yellow lead salts suggest the existence of these acids in the thiol phase. Formation of a blue colour with ferric chloride (aqueous alcoholic), however, indicates thio-thiol tautomerism of the acids,

which also offers an explanation of mutarotation of *d*-thiocamphor-carboxylic acid, $[\alpha]_D^{30}$, 21.03° (in benzene) falling down to $[\alpha]_D^{30}$, 19.56° after 24 hours.

Thiocamphor-carboxylic acid cannot be esterified by the usual method of esterification with alcohol and hydrogen chloride but it gives a methyl ester when methyl iodide acts on the silver salt of the acid. The ester, like the acid shows thio-thiol tautomerism (ferric chloride colouration).

Thiocamphor-dithiocarboxylic acid is obtained by the interaction of dry carbon disulphide and sodiothiocamphor in benzene. The acid is very slowly affected by semicarbazide but when treated with bases like ethylamine, phenylhydrazine etc. sulphuretted hydrogen is readily evolved. When distilled in vacuum it gives carbon disulphide and thiocamphor (*cf.* Tschugaeff and Pigoulewski, *Compt. rend.*, 1911, 163, 388). The analogous behaviour of thiocamphor-dithiocarboxylic acid and camphor-dithiocarboxylic acid and the evolution of hydrogen sulphide with organic bases suggest the formula (III) for the acid. The formation of a deep blue colour with ferric chloride suggests thio-thiol tautomerism, which eliminates the possibility of its being a thioxanthic acid (V).

Methyl thiocamphor -a dithiocarboxylate has been obtained by treatment of sodiothiocamphor in benzene successively with carbon disulphide and dimethyl sulphate, as a light yellow liquid which also gives a blue colour with ferric chloride.

By the condensation of formic ester with sodiothiocamphor, oxymethylenethiocamphor is formed as a light brown liquid which is a strongly acidic substance. It gives a brown copper salt, a yellow mercuric salt, a red colouration with ferric chloride which slowly changes to green and it forms a semicarbazone identical with that of oxymethylenecamphor (*cf.* Wallach and Steindorff, *Annalen*, 1903, 329, 129). These properties suggest the following structures for oxymethylenethiocamphor (*cf.* Bishop, Claisen *et al.*, *Annalen*, 1894, 281, 330; Bredt *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1919, 366, 62; Brühl, *Ber.*, 1904, 37, 2074, etc.).

E X P E R I M E N T A L.

Thiocamphor- α -carboxylic Acid.—Sodithiocamphor was prepared by the usual method in benzene medium. The benzene solution was diluted with ether and a current of carbon dioxide was passed through the solution for 12 hours at 0° and then for 6 hours at the room temperature (39°). The resulting gelatinous mass was poured on to crushed ice and the benzene-ether layer containing unchanged thiocamphor was separated. The aqueous solution was extracted once with ether and then acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid at 0°. An oil separated out which slowly solidified to a colourless solid. It was redissolved in sodium carbonate solution, filtered and reprecipitated with dilute hydrochloric acid. The precipitate on recrystallisation from a mixture of alcohol and ether gave thiocamphor-carboxylic acid as colourless hexagonal plates, m.p. 125°, yield 30%, $[\alpha]_D^{30} + 21.03^\circ$ which falls to $[\alpha]_D^{30} + 19.36^\circ$ after 24 hours (in benzene). (Found: C, 62.64; H, 7.61; Equiv., 211.1. $C_{11}H_{14}O_2S$ requires C, 62.26; H, 7.55 per cent. Equiv., 212).

The *dl*-thiocamphor- α -carboxylic acid, m.p. 121°, was similarly prepared from the sodio derivative of *dl*-thiocamphor. (Found: C, 62.27; H, 7.68; Equiv., 210. $C_{11}H_{14}O_2S$ requires C, 62.26; H, 7.55; Equiv., 212).

These acids are readily soluble in alkalis giving colourless solutions and in organic solvents giving light pink solutions. They give blue colouration with ferric chloride in aqueous alcoholic solutions. The *semicarbazone* crystallised from alcohol as colourless needles, m.p. 133-34°. It is identical with the *semicarbazone* from *d*-camphor- α -carboxylic acid (mixed m.p.). (Found: N, 16.80. Calc. for $C_{12}H_{18}O_2N_2$: N, 16.60 per cent).

l-Thiocamphor from *d*-Thiocamphor- α -carboxylic Acid.—*d*-Thiocamphor- α -carboxylic acid (5 g.) was distilled in vacuum when *l*-thiocamphor sublimed over at 95-100°/5 mm. as a silky orange crystalline substance which was purified by resublimation, yield 3.5 g. *l*-Thiocamphor (m.p. 146°), thus obtained, has $[\alpha]_D^{30} - 24.58^\circ$ (in benzene) and $[\alpha]_D^{30} - 12^\circ$ in ethyl acetate. Thiocamphor, like camphor, thus gives different values for specific rotations in different solvents. (Found: S, 19.17. Calc. for $C_{10}H_{16}S$: S, 19.05 per cent).

Methyl thiocamphor- α -carboxylate was obtained by converting the acid into its silver salt and treating the yellow silver salt with methyl iodide. The silver salt from thiocamphor (2 g.), prepared in the usual way, was washed with alcohol and ether, dried and then refluxed with methyl iodide (5 g.) for 2 hours at 80°. The solution was then cooled, filtered, ether removed

and the residue on crystallisation from alcohol gave the ester as colourless needles, m.p. 96° , yield 1.8 g. It gave a blue colour with aqueous alcoholic ferric chloride. (Found : C, 63.85 ; H, 7.98 ; M.W., 228. $C_{12}H_{10}O_2S$ requires C, 63.71 ; H, 7.96 per cent. M. W. 226).

d-Thiocamphor-a-dithiocarboxylic Acid.—Thiocamphor (10g.) was converted in benzene into the sodio derivative and treated with dry carbon disulphide (10 c.c.) at 0° . After 1 hour, the mixture was refluxed at 80° for 2 hours. It was then cooled, mixed with ice-cold water and extracted with ether. The yellow aqueous solution was cooled to 0° and slowly acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid. A red offensive smelling oil separated out which on keeping for 2-3 days gave a solid which was washed with alcohol to remove the adhering oil. It crystallised from petroleum ether (b.p. $40-50^{\circ}$) as brown needles, m.p. 172° . It is moderately soluble in alcohol and petroleum ether and readily soluble in ether, benzene and chloroform. It gives a blue colour with aqueous alcoholic ferric chloride. It has got a strong mercaptanic smell. The alcoholic solution is deep brown having a green fluorescence. It is *dextrorotatory*, $[\alpha]_D^{20} + 58.03^{\circ}$ in 1% benzene solution. (Found : C, 53.97 ; H, 6.65 ; S, 39.45 ; M.W., 248. $C_{11}H_{10}S_2$ requires C, 54.10 ; H, 6.56 ; S, 39.34 per cent. M.W., 244). The *semicarbazone* crystallised from alcohol as light yellow needles, m.p. 165° . (Found : N, 14.56. $C_{12}H_{10}ON_2S_2$ requires N, 14.74 per cent).

Methylthiocamphor-a-dithiocarboxylate.—Sodio thiocamphor was treated with sodium-dried carbon disulphide at 0° , and then with methyl sulphate. After heating at 100° for 2 hours, the mixture was treated with ice-cold water and extracted with ether. The ethereal solution was dried, evaporated and the residual liquid on distillation gave the ester as a light yellow liquid, b. p. $80^{\circ}/10$ mm., having slight mercaptanic smell ; yield 20 per cent. The compound gives a blue colour with aqueous alcoholic ferric chloride. On keeping it decomposes developing a very strong mercaptanic odour. (Found : C, 55.98 ; H, 7.02 ; S, 37.52. $C_{12}H_8S_2$ requires C, 55.81 ; H, 6.98 ; S, 37.21 per cent).

Oxymethylenethiocamphor.—*l*-Thiocamphor (10 g.) in benzene solution was converted into sodio derivative by molecular sodium, and dry formic ester (6 g.) was added at 0° . After 12 hours, the mixture was poured into crushed ice and the benzene layer after drying over anhydrous sodium sulphate was evaporated. The residual yellow viscous mass was dissolved in alcohol and treated with an aqueous solution of copper acetate, when the dark brown copper salt was precipitated, which crystallised from alcohol as dark brown needles, m.p. $154-55^{\circ}$ (decomp.). [Found : S, 13.92 ; Cu, 14.33. ($C_{12}H_{10}O_2S_2$) Cu requires S, 14.11 ; Cu, 14.02 per cent].

When the alcoholic solution of oxymethylenethiocamphor was treated with mercuric chloride, the mercury salt was obtained which crystallised from alcohol as yellow, silky, prismatic needles, m.p. 125° , $[\alpha]_D^{20}$, $+22.22^{\circ}$ (in benzene). (Found: Hg, 34.10; M.W. 596. $C_{22}H_{20}O_2S_2Hg$ requires Hg, 33.90 per cent. (M.W., 590).

The mercury salt was suspended in alcohol and was freed of mercury by hydrogen sulphide. The alcoholic filtrate was diluted with water and the resulting oil was extracted with ether. The ethereal solution gave oxymethylenethiocamphor as a light brown liquid, b.p. $110-15^{\circ}/5$ mm., yield poor. It is a strongly acidic liquid, readily soluble in sodium carbonate and bicarbonate solutions. It is very unstable. The freshly distilled liquid is light brown, but in the course of a few hours it becomes dark brown and viscous. (Found: C, 67.38; H, 8.22; S, 16.35; M.W., 198. $C_{11}H_{10}OS$ requires C, 67.35; H, 8.16; S, 16.33 per cent. M.W., 196). The *semicarbazone* crystallised from alcohol as colourless needles, m.p. $217-18^{\circ}$. It is identical with the semicarbazone derived from oxymethylenecamphor. (Found: N, 17.83; Calc. for $C_{12}H_{10}O_2N_2$: N, 17.72 per cent).

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